

****HARVARD****

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-1) What is Harvard?

It's a private university located in Cambridge, Massachusetts, USA, Founded in 1636 as a college and named to John Harvard. The campus area is 5,076 acres, and it has 16,000 employees, faculty members, more than 70 libraries, and many

other facilities, Harvard is the oldest high-learning institution in the US which makes it one of the top five most prestigious learning facilities worldwide.

-2) History of Harvard

Harvard University bears the name of the oldest educational facility in the United States, founded on October 8, 1636. The school was renamed after Rev. John Harvard after it was the "New College." After his death, he left some of his

possessions to the university as a collection of books that included about 320 volumes, and he inherited 780 pounds sterling, and for this, it was honored and named after his legacy.

1600: the origin:

University Square House and acres were bought by officials in 1637 from Goodman Peyntree and situated on the southern edge of 'Cow-yard Row' in Cambridge, this small piece of land are now one of the most famous and prestigious universities in the world.

1638-1649

John Harvard gives his library (400 books) and half his estate to the university, Reverend Henry Dunster was appointed the first president of Harvard University,

First Harvard graduation party with nine graduates, The Cambridge city Mr. Henry Dunster give Harvard the "College Farm" at Billerica, Mass., which paid annual rent to the College until 1775 when the farm was sold.

1700: Harvard and the American Revolution

Future U.S. president John Adams graduates Before 1773, Adams graduated 14th in a class of 24, In 1974 Original Harvard Hall burns, destroying some 5,000 volumes and all but one of John Harvard's books.

1800: Century of Growth

18-year presidency started by John Thornton Kirkland, by 1815 University Hall was completed and in 1817 Harvard Law School was established, 1855 Holworthy Hall gets the first gas lights in the entire Yard, 1874 Department of Fine Arts was established.

1900: Century of Progress

In 1901 First course was offered in landscape architecture & city planning, and by 1920 The College Library contained nearly 1,127,500 books, In 1956 Memorial Hall tower burns down, 1959 Fidel Castro is guest of Law School forum, 1980 American Repertory Theater visits Harvard, 1998 Nelson Mandela awarded an honorary degree at special convocation.

2000: fast Evolution

at beginning of 2001, Lawrence Summers was appointed president and in 2004 Harvard Financial Aid Initiative was launched, 2007 Drew Gilpin Faust was the first women Harvard presidents, from 2013 to 2015 the financial aides were helping the university as a token of thanks.

-3) Faculties

Harvard University includes more than 17 prestigious schools, such as medicine, law, engineering, and others. Today, I will touch on three faculties in short, and we will start with the first:

3-1) Law Faculty

Harvard Law School was founded in early 1817 at the request of Isaac Royall and is considered the oldest law school in the United States containing the largest academic legal library in the world, Harvard Law School attracts about 2,000

students annually and are accompanied by about 100 professors on their educational journey to reach their goals. They become judges or lawyers or practice any profession in the field of law. They offer them about 400 courses and seminars every year.

3-2) economy Faculty

In the 19th century, economics and political economy were studied under the general cover of philosophy, and in 1897, economics became separate under the department of history, government, and economics.

From the early 20th century until World War I, Harvard had the strongest economics program in the country. Despite the lack of faculty members and teachers, they have proven their worth

3-3) Faculty of Arts and Sciences

founded in 1890 considered the largest division in Harvard University, led by an academic group under the lead of Mr. Dean Claudine Gay.

they have 502 professors, 6,800 undergraduates, and 4,500 graduate students, and the FAS welcomes about 30,000 new students in a year.

-4) Harvard scholarships

Admission to the Harvard University scholarship is not easy, as there are many applicants for this scholarship and the university chooses the most worthy of it according to strengths and talents.

According to what the university mentioned, they accept nearly half of the university students for scholarships. Of course, this also depends on other factors, and we mention a bit :

- * bachelor's degree.
- * TOFEL score over 110.
- * IELTS score of 75 or more.
- * PTE score over 75.

The duration of the scholarship is according to the years of study prepared for each specialization, on average 3 years.

Unfortunately, Harvard does not offer full scholarships to their students, it must be a contribution from their side, the scholarship amount is calculated on the

student's last 3 years of income. to know more about the scholarships visit our previous scholarship article.